

ePIC PIDs for Instruments in the Sensor Management System

Use Case Analysis

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26 January 2026

Imprint

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Date of publication	26 January 2026
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17733707
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Deliverable	Part of D3.1 in the integration phase of PID4NFDI

About

PID4NFDI (<https://base4nfdi.de/projects/pid4nfdi>) is the basic service for persistent identifiers in development for the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). PID4NFDI is part of and funded through Base4NFDI.

Funded by DFG as part of NFDI. DFG Grant Number: [521453681](#)

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Background

This report describes the integration of PIDs for instruments within the Sensor Management System (SMS). It outlines the PID registration workflow, and discusses the metadata used, including its mapping to the PIDINST metadata schema. It also presents the elaborated curation processes, employed by the Helmholtz Centers involved. For a variety of reasons, the SMS serves as a blueprint on how to implement PID registration for instruments. While registration within the SMS is done via the B2INST service, PID4NFDI also offers a use case report on the Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin, where instruments are registered with DataCite (Boehm 2025).

As further context, PID4NFDI has a variety of resources and services to help you gain the necessary knowledge. To get started, take a look at the instrument chapter within the [PID4NFDI Cookbook](#). If you are looking for specific examples of how to apply metadata fields to instruments, please refer to [Rorie et al. \(2026\)](#). Additionally, [Böhm \(2025\)](#) focuses on linking instrument PIDs to related research entities. Finally, to gain an overview of the landscape of instruments with a PID, consult the [statistics section](#) of our federated search tool ([Springer/Stocker 2025](#)).

Introduction and Motivation

Sensor Management System (SMS) as a component of the digital ecosystem for FAIR time series data management in Earth System Sciences

The [Sensor Management System \(SMS\)](#) is an [open-source](#) platform for the management of sensors, measurement setups, and campaigns. A recent system paper provides an overview of its architecture, governance, and FAIR-oriented design ([Lorenz et al. 2025](#)). In one prominent implementation of a broader landscape of time series management solutions, SMS serves as the first of three independent yet complementary components in a comprehensive digital system for sensor-based time series data ([Bumberger et al. 2025](#)) for the Earth System Sciences. Within that ecosystem, the time series data collected via sensors registered in the SMS are stored and visualized in time.IO, while the System for Automated Quality Control (SaQC) ensures data integrity through automated

curation processes ([Schmidt et al. 2023](#)). Together, these components enable “the ability to represent complete data flows from source to end-user within a unified software system” ([Bumberger et al. 2025](#)). Similar components for time series storage, visualization, and quality control also exist in other centers and infrastructures; the SMS integration described here focuses specifically on the Helmholtz DataHub context.

The SMS, developed collaboratively by the Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences (GFZ), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ), and Jülich Research Centre (FZJ), serves as the foundation for managing devices and their metadata. In addition to supporting standardized metadata management, SMS enables the generation of persistent identifiers (PIDs) for instruments through the SMS API and the user-friendly web interface. Specifically, the EUDAT service [B2INST](#) is used to assign ePIC PIDs to the instruments. This functionality makes it the central entry point for implementing metadata compliant with [PIDINST](#) and linking instrument information to the data lifecycle within the Helmholtz data infrastructure.

Identification, Standardization and Interoperability

There were multiple arguments for adopting persistent identifiers, specifically B2INST, within the SMS. The introduction of instrument PIDs was primarily driven by the need to manage sensor metadata in a standardized way, in accordance with the FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability). As part of a distributed research infrastructure, the SMS needed to ensure that instruments and their metadata could be reliably identified, referenced, and integrated across systems and institutions. Using PIDs enables persistent, machine-actionable links between instruments and the data they produce, supporting transparent data provenance and long-term traceability – an important prerequisite for AI-ready pipelines where software agents can discover, interpret, and reuse instrument context without manual intervention (see [Brinckmann et al. 2024a](#) for a concise overview of the pivotal arguments for PID integration into the SMS).

The four Helmholtz Centers from the Research Field Earth and Environment opted for B2INST, as it fully implements the [PIDINST metadata schema](#) aligning the SMS with a recognized community standard for describing and referencing research instruments. With DataCite as the alternative, there are no dedicated fields for

instrument-specific information such as the instrument type, model name and measured variables.

Beyond these technical advantages, B2INST is a European service contributing to the EOSC ecosystem, making it particularly suitable for infrastructures with an international scope, such as ERICs. Thus, the adoption of B2INST ensures both schema compatibility and alignment with European FAIR and Open Science frameworks (see also [Brinckmann 2024](#) on the reasons for choosing B2INST).

PID Registration Workflow

The registration of a PID in the Sensor Management System (SMS) is directly linked to the creation of an instrument record. A PID can only be assigned to a device that already exists in the SMS, and the same group of users that create a SMS record typically registers a PID for the device. Therefore, before describing the PID registration itself, it is necessary to outline how instruments are created and managed within the system.

In principle, all researchers at the participating Helmholtz Centers are authorized to create new devices in the SMS. In practice, however, this task is mainly performed by scientific and technical staff, as they possess the necessary detailed knowledge of specifications and metadata. At the GFZ, dedicated device managers have been explicitly appointed for each section, who will gradually assume greater responsibility for creating and maintaining device records. This establishes a governance model in which general authorization is broadly granted, but practical responsibility lies with trained or designated individuals. The SMS thus follows a user “self-service approach” ([Bumberger et al. 2025](#)) that allows researchers and technical staff to create and curate instrument entries directly, ensuring that metadata are captured as close as possible to the source of expertise.

When a new device is created in the SMS – via API or the web interface – the responsible user can optionally trigger the registration of a PID via B2INST (see the python code for the [B2INST extension](#)). Alternatively, the identifier can be assigned at a later point when editing the device’s metadata record. Once registered, updates to the instrument metadata in the SMS are automatically synchronized with B2INST. Therefore, for SMS-users, registering a PID via B2INST essentially amounts to ticking a box. Deciding whether to obtain a PID and whether the public

provision of a subset of metadata of the SMS record is useful is more time-consuming than creating the PID itself.

Which Devices get PIDs?

The individuals responsible for the management of a given instrument decide themselves whether to add a PID. In the SMS, PIDs proved to be especially important for instruments used within projects that span multiple Helmholtz Centers and potentially external partners. While the decision for or against PID registration is therefore criteria driven, just to give a vague benchmark, about half of all devices across the three instances of the SMS that already use the B2INST extension have a PID.

At B2INST, users need to assign themselves to a community to register instruments. In the case of the SMS, it is the [Helmholtz Research Field \(RF\) Earth and Environment community](#). As of November 2025, 1,777 registered instruments are associated with this community. This amounts to 80% of all instruments registered with B2INST (n: 2,220). The use of the SMS and the allocation of PIDs depends on the priorities of the individual organization resulting in some variation. Specifically, 1,333 devices have been registered via the SMS instance operated by [GFZ](#), 184 at [KIT](#), and 260 at [UFZ](#).¹

Given the consistent use of controlled vocabulary for key properties (see below), it is easy to get an overview of the registered devices and their measurement outputs. The spectrum ranges from simple sensors and data loggers to complex measuring stations. Data loggers (n: 619), thermometers (n: 205) and combined soil moisture and temperature sensors (n: 179) are particularly well represented. In addition, there are numerous specialized measuring devices such as sound transducers, hydrostatic pressure transducers, redox potential sensors, disdrometers, lidar systems, and weather stations.

The associated measured variables reflect the diversity of environmental and atmospheric research. Most commonly recorded are temperature (soil, air, water), humidity, pressure, electrical conductivity, redox potential, and various radiation components. Numerous sensors also capture atmospheric trace gases (CO₂, CH₄,

¹ The productive SMS instance at the [FZJ](#) is the youngest of all Helmholtz SMS instances with B2INST not yet implemented.

NO₂, O₃, SO₂), precipitation characteristics (intensity, drop-size distribution), and wind parameters.

Metadata

The development of the SMS data model as a whole followed an iterative process based on user requirements, community feedback, and the established terminology within the respective application domains. As development progressed, elements and concepts from the [OGC SensorThings API](#) data model were increasingly adopted and adapted. This also applies to the metadata used for devices. It was therefore developed independently of the PIDINST metadata schema originally. However, for the integration of persistent identifiers PIDINST was fully adopted, and SMS entries were mapped to PIDINST accordingly (see Table 1 and the respective python module for the [mapping](#)).

The mapping proved to be largely straightforward. This may be partly due to the fact that the British Oceanographic Data Centre ([BODC](#)), one of the key use cases involved in the development of the PIDINST metadata schema, had also described its instrument inventory using OGC SensorML open standards ([Stocker et al. 2020: 6](#)). Nevertheless, it was also a learning process resulting in slight changes over time. Regarding the owner of the device, for example, there was the realization that institutional attribution, i.e., referencing the hosting institution rather than individual persons, provides greater long-term stability and clarity.

The SMS instances all use the same data model. This entails the [obligation levels for the properties](#) being the same. It has been a conscious decision to keep the number of mandatory metadata fields low to reduce the entry barrier for using the system and encouraging a broad adoption. The aim is to allow devices to be described in a straightforward manner, with the option to gradually enrich the records over time. This is a pragmatic decision to increase the acceptance in the community, which is crucial given the user self-serve approach.

Because of this, it is even more important that the associated metadata are automatically synchronized with B2INST whenever a user alters the respective SMS record. It reduces maintenance costs and it helps to avoid inconsistencies that could undermine metadata quality. While the metadata completeness varies across the SMS instances of the Helmholtz Centers, the overall coverage of attributes is comparatively high. One current limitation is that related identifiers are not yet

used, which could, for example, be an option to link two instruments such as a sensor and a data logger (see our [recommendations for linking instruments](#)).

B2INST allows for community extensions of the PIDINST metadata schema. The [Helmholtz Research Field \(RF\) Earth and Environment community](#) does not use the feature as of yet. However, potential properties already considered in the SMS that are missing in the PIDINST metadata schema have been identified as potential candidates, i.e., attributes that are covered often and are rarely subject to change like manuals or images of the instrument and other attachments.²

Table 1: PIDINST (B2INST) to SMS Mapping (devices only).

PIDINST	SMS			
	Obl.	Property	Obl.	Occ.
Identifier	M	persistent_identifier	O ¹	1
identifierType	M	set by B2INST ("Handle")	M	1
SchemaVersion	M	set by B2INST ("1.0") ²	M	1
LandingPage	M	landing_page	M	1
Name	M	"short.name - device.manufacturer_name - device.model - device.serial_number"	M ³	1
Owner	M		M	1-n
ownerName	M	contact.organization ⁴	M	1
ownerContact	O	-	-	0-1
ownerIdentifier	O	-	-	0-1
ownerIdentifierType	O	-	-	1
Manufacturer	M		O	1-n
manufacturerName	M	device.manufacturer_name	O	1
manufacturerIdentifier	O	device.manufacturer_uri	O	0-1
manufacturerIdentifierType	O	if CV used: "URL"	O	1
Model	R		O	0-1
modelName	R	device.model	O	1

² Although the purpose of community extensions is to fulfil the specific needs of a given community, it could still be helpful to look at examples such as [ACTRIS](#) and [Sensor.Community](#) to see what properties an extension to the metadata schema might entail.

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modelIdentifier	O	-	0	0-1
modelIdentifierType	O	-	0	1
Description	R	device.description	0	0-1
InstrumentType	R		0	0-n
instrumentTypeName	R	device.device_type_name	0	1
instrumentTypeIdentifier	O	device.device_type_uri	0	0-1
instrumentTypeIdentifierType	O	if CV used: "URL"	0	1
MeasuredVariable	R	device.device_properties.property_name	0	0-n
Date	R	-	- ⁵	0-n
dateType	R	-	-	1
RelatedIdentifier	R	-	-	0-n
relatedIdentifierType	R	-	-	1
relationType	R	-	-	1
relatedIdentifierName	O	-	-	0-1
AlternateIdentifier	R	serial_number or inventory_number or landing_page	0	0-n
alternateIdentifierType	R	" serial number " or " inventory number " or "Other"	0	1
alternateIdentifierName	O	only used if AlternateIdentifier = landing_page , then it is "URL"	0	0-1

¹ Obligation levels do not need to be differentiated for records with or without a PID, since using B2INST does not incur any additional obligations. The persistent identifier itself is the only exception to this.

² As of November 2025, the PIDINST schema is still on version 1.0.

³ As "short_name" is a mandatory attribute in the SMS, there will always be a valid instrument name when registering via B2INST. However, the number of elements the name consists of varies because the other considered properties are optional.

⁴ The decision has been made to change from giving information on the individual responsible for the instrument to referencing the hosting institution, which is in line with the PIDINST recommendation.

⁵ Dates are not used for devices, the B2INST record therefore has only its creation date and the date of the last update of the record as information in date format.

Curation

The curation of instrument metadata in the Sensor Management System (SMS) focuses on structural control rather than retrospective corrections. It achieves this through controlled vocabulary and data models, as well as support mechanisms for users to promote quality and consistency. Regarding the latter, the [SMS Wiki](#) provides its users with detailed information on the functionality of the platform. Among its contents are [tutorial videos](#), [FAQs](#), a help page for the [creation and editing of devices](#), and documents on [best practices](#) with specific examples of the different entities within the SMS.

All SMS instances operated by Helmholtz Centres use a shared central [vocabulary server](#). This server provides harmonized terminology for key PIDINST metadata elements, including manufacturer and instrument type. The latter is especially of note, as there are only a few domain-specific ontologies for instrument types, with only the [SeaVoX Device Catalogue](#) being actually used for metadata of instruments with PIDs so far. The identifier fields of the PIDINST metadata schema are used to reference the corresponding terms in the controlled vocabulary. Measured variables are the only exception: although the SMS uses controlled vocabulary identifiers for them, the PIDINST metadata schema does not offer a dedicated identifier field. Instead, measured variables are stored in B2INST as a single free-text field. This limitation highlights a potential area for improvement in the PIDINST metadata schema, as the SMS demonstrates the value of using controlled terms also for measured variables.

For the specifics on how terms are curated, see the entry about the [process](#) in the SMS Wiki, which also gives a list of sources to frequent in order to keep suggestions in line with existing ontologies wherever possible. It is a transparent process with every pending decision for a new term getting its own [issue](#) in the repository. Terms are discussed at the meetings of the [curation team](#) or the monthly [community meetings](#), too. The curation process thus fits the general pattern of community-driven development of the SMS. Overall, the curation efforts have the objective of ensuring high metadata quality while still maintaining a low entry barrier consistent with the user self-service approach of the SMS.

Example PID: ADCP QLiner 2 - OTT HydroMet - QLiner2 (1 MHz) - 275539-2240500120

The ePIC PID **21.11157/86e53e2e-eb5c-44ab-852d-2d0c2313572c** uniquely identifies the “ADCP QLiner 2”. It is an acoustic doppler current profiler managed within the GFZ SMS instance. The instrument record at the PID provider includes all standardized metadata transmitted to B2INST. The landing page at the SMS has additional information, such as keywords and images, and is fully publicly accessible:

The ePIC DOI has the following components/links:

- ePIC DOI (displayed as URL together with its resolver):
<http://hdl.handle.net/21.11157/86e53e2e-eb5c-44ab-852d-2d0c2313572c>
- Landing page: The DOI resolves to an entry in the SMS database representing the acoustic doppler current profiler, available at the URL
<https://sensors.gfz.de/devices/765>
- B2INST website: The DOI information and metadata is available at
<https://b2inst.gwdg.de/records/86e53e2eeb5c44ab852d2d0c2313572c>
- B2INST Metadata: The B2INST metadata can be downloaded in JSON format via the EUDAT B2INST HTTP REST API:
<https://b2inst.gwdg.de/api/records/86e53e2eeb5c44ab852d2d0c2313572c>

Main Takeaways

How organizations adopt instrument PIDs depends strongly on their specific requirements and workflows. What matters is a coherent overall strategy, and in this regard the SMS provides several important lessons. The Helmholtz Centers deliberately designed their approach with community acceptance at its core. This is crucial because the SMS follows a user-self-service model: there is no centralized instrument registration. Instead, researchers and technical staff add devices themselves. For this to work, every design choice had to support usability, consistency, and low barriers.

The user interfaces, both via API and web, were designed to make device registration straightforward, while a comprehensive Wiki provides detailed guidance for practical implementation. Feedback mechanisms, such as community meetings and GitLab issue tracking, ensure alignment with user needs. Although

SMS is technically mature, it continues to evolve in response to community feedback, which can be seen in ongoing repository commits. The controlled vocabulary, curated by the community, provides a harmonized set of terms relevant to instrument metadata, reducing the effort required for new users and ensuring semantic consistency. Moreover, PIDs can be minted without redundant metadata entry, minimizing practical and technical barriers. This combination of design choices helps ensure that instrument PID registration is seamlessly integrated into the operational workflows of the system. AI-ready by design: The combination of PIDINST-aligned metadata, controlled vocabulary identifiers, and fully supported APIs (including JSON export) enables machine-actionable integration into catalogs, knowledge graphs, and automated data pipelines. This lowers the effort for downstream reuse and supports scalable analytics, including AI/ML workflows that rely on consistent, well-identified instrument context.

The effectiveness of this approach is evidenced by the Helmholtz Research Field (RF) Earth and Environment being the largest B2INST community. The involved Helmholtz Centers aim for the wider adoption of this open-source platform ([Louisot et al. 2025](#)) that “offers sufficient flexibility for use in other domains as well as individual extension and customization possibilities due to the use of common standards” ([Brinckmann 2024](#)). The recent initialisation of an instance operated by the British Oceanographic Data Centre of the National Oceanography Centre (BODC-NOC) might be an indicator that this endeavor is successful, potentially contributing to a broader uptake of instrument PIDs and of the B2INST service more generally. In addition, an “Instance for the NFDI4Earth context in Germany, eLTER RI and the EOSC cloud [is] in preparation” ([Brinckmann 2024a](#)).

As one of the first examples of consistent, efficient, and technically mature integration of instrument PIDs, SMS can serve as a blueprint for other equipment databases. Beyond the technical components, its design principles – ranging from PID provider choice to workflow integration, controlled vocabulary, metadata mapping, and user support – highlight the importance of a coherent concept for instrument PID adoption.

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